

HISTORICAL ARTIFACTS SMUGGLED ABROAD FROM ANATOLIAN LANDS AND CULTURAL HERITAGE

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Abstract. *Anatolia has hosted many civilizations throughout history, and the artifacts left by these civilizations have reached the present day as a valuable cultural heritage. This study focuses on the prevention of illegal smuggling of historical artifacts abroad and the processes of repatriating these artifacts to their original lands. It highlights the pioneering work of Osman Hamdi Bey in the protection of cultural heritage and the current efforts for repatriation. Furthermore, this study emphasizes that cultural heritage not only shapes the past but also the future, and forms the foundational stones of social identity and unity. In this context, increasing the awareness of society and individuals is critically important for the protection of cultural heritage. The preservation of cultural heritage is stressed as a responsibility that is not only national but also international.*

Keywords: *Cultural Heritage, Anatolia, Smuggling of Historical Artifacts.*

Аннотация. *Анатолия на протяжении истории была местом обитания многих цивилизаций, и артефакты, оставленные этими цивилизациями, дошли до наших дней как ценное культурное наследие. Это исследование сосредоточено на предотвращении незаконного вывоза исторических артефактов за границу и процессах возвращения этих артефактов в их исходные места. В нем подчеркивается пионерская работа Османа Хамди Бея в области защиты культурного наследия и текущие усилия по возвращению. Кроме того, в исследовании подчеркивается, что культурное наследие формирует не только прошлое, но и будущее, и является основой социальной идентичности и единства. В этом контексте критически важно повышение осведомленности общества и отдельных лиц для защиты культурного наследия. Подчеркивается, что сохранение культурного наследия является ответственностью, которая носит не только национальный, но и международный характер.*

Ключевые слова: *Культурное наследие, Анатолия, Контрабанда исторических артефактов.*

Annotatsiya. *Anadolu tarix davomida ko'plab tsivilizatsiyalarga mezbonlik qilgan bo'lib, ushbu tsivilizatsiyalardan qolgan asarlar bugungi kunda qimmatli madaniy meros sifatida yetib kelgan. Ushbu tadqiqot tarixiy asarlarning noqonuniy yo'llar bilan xorijga olib chiqilishining oldini olish va ushbu asarlarni asl joylariga qaytarish jarayonlariga e'tibor qaratadi, Osman Hamdi Beyning madaniy merosni himoya qilishdagi pioner ishlariga va hozirgi qaytarish harakatlariga diqqat qiladi. Shuningdek, bu tadqiqotda madaniy meros faqat o'tmishni emas, balki kelajakni ham shakllantirishi va jamiyatning hamda birlikning asosiy tushunchalarini yaratishi ta'kidlanadi. Shu kontekstda, jamiyat va shaxslarning sezgirligini oshirish madaniy merosni himoya qilish uchun juda muhimdir. Madaniy merosni himoya qilish faqat milliy emas, balki xalqaro mas'uliyat ekanligi ta'kidlanadi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *Madaniy Meros, Anadolu, Tarixiy Asarlar Kontrabandasi.*

1. Introduction

Anatolian lands have hosted many civilizations from the depths of history to the present day, and the cultural heritage left by these civilizations has formed the basis of our rich cultural texture today. Preserving cultural heritage and passing it on to future generations is not only a national issue but also an international responsibility. The protection of cultural assets is of great importance internationally. The identification and return of illegally exported cultural assets to their original location should be supported by the necessary legal frameworks. According to the Eurobarometer report (2017), 84% of Europeans find cultural heritage personally important and 80% think it is also important for the European Union. These rates show that cultural heritage is not just remnants of the past, but also the cornerstones of social identity and unity.

The plunder of cultural heritage and the smuggling of historical artifacts abroad are considered as a part of the cultural hegemony and identity construction processes of imperialist and colonialist powers. Such practices, it is argued, serve the symbolic annexation of the 'other' by usurping and reinterpreting the cultural achievements of colonized peoples. Postcolonial critique and decolonization efforts call for recognizing these historical injustices and questioning the ongoing effects of colonial practices on existing cultural and social structures (Varela and Dhawan: 2020).

According to the laws of the Republic of Turkey, Article 5 of the Law on the Protection of Cultural and Natural Assets No. 2863 emphasizes that movable and immovable cultural assets are state property. Acts of illegal selling to other countries or individuals have not been completely prevented throughout history, despite serious criminal sanctions. From the Ottoman Empire to the present day, thousands of historical artifacts have been taken abroad illegally. However, thanks to the recently increased diplomatic efforts and the meticulous work of archaeologists and researchers, many artifacts have been returned to their original locations. In this article, important works exhibited and recorded in museums abroad will be introduced and stories about how they were removed illegally will be included.

In addition, despite all legal measures and controls and successful return processes, the most important element that can prevent the preservation of historical artifacts and their illegal export abroad is to increase the awareness of society and individuals. This sensitivity is possible not only through information and education, but also by making the society feel that it belongs to its own culture by establishing a direct connection with these historical works. As Halicarnassus Fisherman Cevat Şakir Kabaağaçlı emphasizes, it is of great importance to embed the understanding in society that "those who live in a country are the heirs of all cultures that lived in that land before them". This perspective plays a critical role in raising social awareness for the protection of works that are the intrinsic property of Anatolian lands. This study aims to emphasize the importance of studies carried out in line with these principles.

2. Why is it important to protect cultural heritage?

Humanity is obliged to transmit the wisdom and riches of the past to future generations. This transfer includes preserving and developing both material and spiritual values and passing them on to the next generations. Thus, the preservation of cultural heritage becomes one of the cornerstones of a community's existence.

Cultural heritage shapes the spirit and identity of a society. Preserving both material and spiritual elements builds bridges between the past and the present and creates a solid sense of belonging built on the values and traditions of the society. This allows individuals to express themselves better and establish deep connections with each other. It also provides valuable information about a community's way of life, beliefs and achievements. Preserving this heritage

reinforces historical awareness and the capacity to shape the future with lessons learned from the past.

Today, with the economic contributions of the tourism industry, sensitivity on historical sites and museums has increased. The visit of hundreds of thousands of tourists to these places not only increases the value of the works exhibited there, but also makes significant contributions to the economy of the host country. While the preservation of cultural heritage constitutes a major attraction in terms of tourism, ancient cities, open-air museums, festivals and various cultural events make significant contributions to the economy. Therefore, the preservation of cultural heritage is of vital importance for the sustainability of societies and the preservation of cultural diversity.

3. Historical Artifacts Smuggled from Anatolia: Transporting Cultural Heritage Abroad

Anatolia is a region that has hosted many civilizations in various periods of history and contains rich cultural heritage from these civilizations. Anatolia has been the cradle of many civilizations, from the Hittites to the Lydians, from the Phrygians to the Carians. Traces of these multi-layered civilizations are discovered deep in Anatolia. Anatolia's culture, which includes these rich civilizations, is important as the beginning and also the future of the common heritage of human history (Yetkin, Yılmaz and Kozak: 2018: 131). However, especially in the 19th century and later, a significant part of this heritage was smuggled abroad, both with legal permission and illegally. Exhibiting these works on their own lands, as a part of the human heritage, is both a requirement of human ethics and an obligation of national and international law.

Osman Hamdi Bey played a leading role in the preservation of cultural heritage and the development of museology in Turkey. As the founder of the Museum-i Hümayun (Istanbul Archaeological Museums), he took important steps in the domestic preservation and exhibition of historical artifacts unearthed from Anatolian lands. These studies are of great importance in terms of preserving cultural heritage and strengthening national identity. The phrase *Ex Oriente Lux* emphasizes that civilization rose from the east. Archaeologist Fahri Işık claims that civilization emerged from Anatolia (Işık: 2019). Considering the artifacts smuggled from Anatolia, it is observed that many artifacts were removed from the birthplace of civilization. These works should be considered as the lost light of Anatolia.

3.1. Nereids Monument (British Museum, England):

Nereids Monument is an important archaeological artifact from the depths of history, located in Xanthos, the ancient capital of Lycia. This monument, thought to have been built around 390 BC in the name of Arbinas, king of the Xanthos Dynasty that ruled western Lycia under the Achaemenid Empire, is known as the largest temple-planned mausoleum of the ancient period and the first temple-planned mausoleum in Anatolia. The Nereid Monument is a structure that reveals the influence of both Persian and Greek cultures on the Lycian civilization. The name of the monument comes from the Nereid statues, known as water nymphs, placed between its columns. These sculptures highlight both the artistic and historical significance of the monument. Discovered by Charles Fellows in 1840, the Nereid Monument was almost completely dismantled and taken to England shortly after its discovery. Today, the reconstruction of this unique work is among the most important works of the British Museum in London. The Nereid Monument is a part of Turkey's rich cultural heritage and has an important place among the unique works that shed light on world history.

3.2. Zeus Altar (Pergamon Museum, Germany):

Zeus Altar is considered one of the most magnificent structures of the ancient city of Pergamon. In 180 BC, King of Pergamon II. This altar, built during the reign of Eumenes, after his victory over the Galatians, attracts attention with its size and architectural features. The altar is 10 meters high, 35 meters wide and 33 meters deep, having the dimensions of a temple. This structure, which is large enough to fit into the inner courtyard of the Temple of Athena, is considered one of the most important works of plastic art of the Hellenistic period.

Among the most striking features of the Zeus Altar are the reliefs depicting the mythological war between the gods and the giants (Gigants). These reliefs represent the pinnacle of the art of the Hellenistic period and are considered an important part of the altar. The Telephos Frieze, located in the courtyard of the altar, tells the heroic and mythological origins of the Attalos Dynasty. This magnificent structure was discovered by German engineer Carl Humann in the 1870s and transported to Prussia at that time, and today it is exhibited in the Pergamon Museum in Berlin. This work, also known as the Zeus Altar or the Great Altar, has taken its place in history as one of the most striking examples of the art and architecture of the Hellenistic period.

3.3. Propylon of the Temple of Athena (Pergamon Museum, Germany):

This structure, built in Pergamon in the 2nd century BC, is known for its remarkable columns and reliefs dedicated to Athena by King Eumenes. It was taken to Germany in the 19th century and is currently in the Pergamon Museum in Berlin.

3.4. Ancient City of Miletus - Agora Gate (Pergamon Museum, Germany):

This impressive gate served as the entrance to the marketplace of the Ancient City of Miletus and was moved to Germany in the late 19th century.

3.5. Lion of Knidos (British Museum, England):

This huge marble lion statue, made in the 2nd century BC, was unearthed from the Ancient City of Knidos and taken to England in the 19th century. The huge marble Lion of Knidos, unearthed from the ancient city of Knidos on the southwestern coast of Turkey, is thought to have been made in the 2nd century BC and is located in the British Museum.

3.6. Aphrodisias Ancient City - Old Fisherman Statue (Pergamon Museum, Germany):

The body of this statue, unearthed from Aphrodisias, was taken to Germany in the late 19th century, and its head and arms were later found in Aphrodisias and were taken under protection in Turkey. The head part of the Old Fisherman Statue located in the Aphrodisias Ancient City in Aydın is located in the Old Museum in Berlin. Another work from Halicarnassus is a mosaic from the Late Roman period containing the Greek words Health, Life, Joy, Peace, Joy and Hope. This work dates back to the 4th century AD and is now in the British Museum collection. The bronze bust of Aphrodite, found in the Ancient City of Satala, dates back to the 1st century BC and is also in the British Museum.

3.7. The Three Graces Mosaic and the Seasons Mosaic in Antakya:

Just like the works exhibited in the collections of the Louvre Museum, the Ruins of the Halicarnassus Mausoleum are also included in the rich collections of the British Museum. The floor mosaic from the Roman period, depicting Hermes and the baby Dionysus, and the mosaic works depicting the Drinking Contest between Hercules and Dionysus are among the prominent pieces of the Worcester Museum of Art.

In addition to the examples mentioned above, many artifacts of various sizes have been smuggled abroad. For example, the Athena Temple Propylon taken from the Ancient City of Pergamon is exhibited in the Pergamon Museum; The Payava Sarcophagus, unearthed from the

Ancient City of Xanthos, is presented to visitors at the British Museum. The Tykhe statue from the Ancient City of Perge in Antalya is in the Royal Museum of Art in Brussels; Idrimi Statue, unearthed from the Ancient Alalah region in Hatay, is in the British Museum; The Head of Dionysus obtained from Smyrna is exhibited in the Dutch National Archaeological Museum, and the "Zion Artifacts" from the Korydalla Ancient City of Antalya are exhibited in the Dumbarton Oaks Museum.

These works provide valuable information on ancient art and history and play an important role in the protection and promotion of cultural heritage. The removal of these works, which are considered living parts of cultural heritage in the museums where they are exhibited, from their countries of origin has brought to the agenda important discussions on the protection and return of cultural heritage. Efforts at the international level to return them to their countries of origin are of great importance for the protection and restoration of cultural heritage.

3.8. Priam's Treasure and Troy Treasures Exhibited in the Pushkin Museum

The excavations carried out by Heinrich Schliemann in the ancient city of Troy in the last quarter of the nineteenth century were considered an important discovery in the field of archaeology. During his work between 1872 and 1890, Schliemann created a collection of 259 items known as the "Treasure of Troy" or "Treasure of Priam". This collection included rare artifacts such as jewelry, vessels, anthropomorphic figures, ax heads and bergcrystal objects. In particular, B.C. It dates back to 2400-2200 and dates back to Troy II. The Great Diadem, found in the layer 1, stands out as an outstanding example of ancient jewelery art. Schliemann's smuggling of these works to Athens after his discovery and their subsequent transfer to the Pushkin Museum triggered an important debate on the protection and return of cultural heritage.

Since 1945, these treasures have been exhibited at the Staatliches Museum für Bildende Künste A. S. Pushkin. Of the 17 treasures preserved in Berlin since 1881, 13 were transported to Moscow and these artifacts were evaluated as "priceless" by German experts in 1939. While a large part of this collection exhibited in the Pushkin Museum consists of precious metals and stones, other works included in the collection are mostly made of bronze and ceramic materials and are in St. It is located in the Staatlichen Eremitage in St. Petersburg. The ongoing diplomatic efforts since 1991 for the return of the Troy treasures and especially the Great Diadem to Turkey as cultural heritage emphasize the importance of protection of cultural heritage and international law. These works, which can be seen in the photographs of Schliemann's wife Sophia Schliemann, have a special importance for the Turkish cultural heritage, although they are scattered around the world.

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